

Gap Analysis for Smart Contract Standardisation

Soumya Kanti Datta
Digiotech, France
soumya@digiotech.com

Abstract— Although smart contracts have emerged as a key innovation for industries, siloed development and deployment of smart contracts pose numerous challenges to mass adoption and interoperability. This paper presents a comprehensive gap analysis of current standardisation efforts in smart contracts, focusing on common requirements, data formats, schema, and software templates. Through an examination of existing standards, best practices, and identified gaps, this paper proposes contributions to address these challenges. By advocating for cross-platform compatibility, scalability, and maintainability, it aims to advance the standardisation of smart contracts and foster their broader adoption in the industry.

Keywords — *Blockchain; Smart Contract.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of blockchain technology has heralded a transformative era in digital transactions, introducing a decentralized architecture that offers a robust alternative to traditional, centralised processing systems. One of the key applications powered by blockchain is a smart contract [1], a self-executing programme recording terms of agreement directly into written code and automating the fulfilment of such predetermined agreement conditions. While most common applications used for smart contracts are cryptocurrency related, the use cases span many industry verticals. One of the unique selling points of smart contracts is that they eliminate the need for intermediaries, reducing transaction costs and streamlining processes for contracts. Their immutability on the blockchain ensures tamper-proof record-keeping and fosters trust in a decentralized environment that involve multiple parties in the contract.

While their numerous advantages have been demonstrated in the state-of-the-art, lack of standardisation in smart contracts prevents a widespread adoption. The current landscape is characterized by a proliferation of numerous smart contracts, each adhering to its own development language, format, execution environment, and interoperability guidelines [2]. The execution of smart contracts on different blockchains involves varying fees and computational demands, making it a complex issue to resolve. This heterogeneity adds on to the complexity of application development, testing, and deployment through several challenges. Firstly, it exposes interoperability gaps [3] among blockchain platforms which in turn limits the potential for seamless cross-platform interaction and data exchange. Secondly, the absence of standardised templates and best practices makes smart contracts vulnerable to security exploits, as evidenced by numerous high-profile hacks in recent years. Finally, the lack of harmonised formats, templates create a barrier for entry to new developers, requiring them to learn specific programming languages and tools for each platform. Cross-chain communication, a relatively new solution has gained research traction as a means of tackling such increasing fragmentation of blockchain networks and scalability through solutions such as sidechaining and sharding [4]. However, due to high

blockchain infrastructure cost and performance requirements for scalability, such solutions are not yet widely adopted [5].

For a mass adoption of smart contracts and their exploitation to full capabilities, industrial standardisation is an imperative. This paper presents a gap analysis conducted by identifying areas within smart contract development that necessitate standard development. By systematically exploring the existing landscape and ongoing standardisation efforts, the author aims to shed lights on the critical gaps preventing interoperability, security, and developer accessibility. The reported findings are going to pave the way for the development of robust and comprehensive European and international standards, propelling smart contracts towards its transformative impact on industries and societies.

II. GAP ANALYSIS IN SMART CONTRACT STANDARDISATION

The extensive gap analysis presented in this paper has been performed as a preparatory work leading towards identifying grounds for standardisation. The gap analysis study investigates the current landscape from a software development perspective, elaborating on common requirements for smart contract development, data formats, templates for smart contract development, and reference architecture for integration with blockchains. From the gap analysis, the work seeks to address key identified challenges by defining uniform requirements and protocols for smart contract development. It will contribute mainly to – (a) defining a unified data structure and schema that will facilitate seamless interaction and integration of smart contracts with various blockchains, (b) standardising the structure and functionality of smart contracts through computational templates to ensure consistent performance across different blockchain platforms, and (c) creating a blueprint for integrating standardised smart contracts with existing blockchain infrastructures, enhancing system interoperability and efficiency.

A. Common requirements for smart contract development

The current state includes international standards for developing smart contracts vary widely among blockchain platforms, leading to issues in security, efficiency, and interoperability. Notable frameworks like Ethereum and Hyperledger Fabric provide their own development environments and languages (e.g., Solidity for Ethereum and Chaincode for Hyperledger), which are not interoperable. ISO/TC 307 is one international effort aimed at standardization in blockchain and distributed ledger technologies, but specific guidelines for smart contract development are still underdeveloped. The gaps identified for common requirements for smart contract software development include but not limited to –

- **Development methodology:** Lack of standardized development methodologies leads to inefficiencies and errors. A standard process model for the lifecycle

of smart contract development could include stages such as requirement gathering, design, coding, testing, deployment, and maintenance.

- **Error handling:** There is no uniform practice on how to handle execution errors in smart contracts. This varies from one blockchain to another, leading to unpredictability in error handling and silo effects.
- **Upgradeability:** While smart contracts are designed to be immutable (taking benefit of blockchain's nature) industrial usability requires methods for upgrading contracts and/or correcting them in response to bugs or evolving business needs and scenarios.
- **Interoperability:** With multiple blockchain platforms in use, each supporting different smart contract languages and environments, cross-chain interoperability is minimal and, in many cases, non-existent. Standardising smart contract interfaces for cross-chain deployment will facilitate interoperability.
- **Security standards:** There is no universally accepted security standard [6] for smart contracts, despite frequently reported vulnerabilities and breaches. A common set of security standards, including security patterns and anti-patterns, is crucial.
- **Legal enforceability:** While efforts like the Uniform Law Commission's smart contract model code explore legal aspects, a gap remains in standardizing how legal terms can be translated into unambiguous code within smart contracts.

B. Data formats, structures, and schema

Smart contracts interact with and integrate several types of data, but there is a significant lack of standardised data formats or schema. Each blockchain has its structure of handling data, which can range from simple key-value stores to more sophisticated storage solutions. This variation complicates data integration and consistency across different blockchain systems. The gaps identified in this regard cover the following.

- **Standard data structures:** There is a need for universally recognized data structures that can be used across various blockchain technologies. These would facilitate easier data sharing and manipulation within and across blockchains. Existing standards like ERC-20 for tokens on Ethereum offer some level of data format consistency. However, a gap exists in creating a more comprehensive standard encompassing different data types used in various smart contract functionalities.
- **Encoding standards:** There is a lack of standardization in how data is encoded and decoded across different blockchains, which affects the data exchange and interoperability.
- **Schema definitions:** Clear definitions and standards for schema design specific to blockchain use cases are lacking. Standard schema would ensure that data stored in smart contracts is consistent, reliable, and predictable.

- **Versioning and updating:** Handling updates to data structures without breaking existing or deployed contracts is a challenge. Standard protocols for versioning of data schema used in smart contracts could help manage evolutionary changes.
- **Data provenance:** While standards like W3C Provenance address data tracking, a gap exists in standardizing how data provenance can be embedded within smart contracts to ensure data integrity and data audit.

C. Templates for smart contract development

Templates are standardized blueprints that can be used to deploy smart contracts that meet specific criteria, ensuring compliance, interoperability, and reliability. Such templates will also shorten time to develop, test, and deploy smart contracts on different blockchains. However, a closer look at the current initiatives and popular blockchain platforms reveal many shortcomings in this regard.

- **Lack of template libraries for reusability:** There are efforts like OpenZeppelin Contracts offering reusable smart contract components. However, a gap exists in creating a standardized library of templates for common functionalities (e.g., escrow, voting) across different blockchain platforms. There is a scarcity of comprehensive, standardized template libraries that cater to various industry needs, which impedes widespread adoption and reuse.
- **Version control:** Template versioning for smart contracts is not widely practiced, making it hard to track changes or revert to previous versions when needed.
- **Customisability and maintainability:** While some templates offer high customizability, there is often a trade-off with complexity, making them less accessible to non-experts. Standardisation efforts often lack clear guidelines for modularity and upgradability within smart contract templates, creating a gap in ensuring long-term maintainability.

D. Reference architecture for integration with blockchains

While some efforts like the Enterprise Ethereum Alliance provide reference architectures for specific blockchain environments, comprehensive architecture that integrates smart contracts across different blockchain platforms is missing. Current architectures focus on single-platform solutions only and do not address cross-platform integration. For example, the integration of smart contracts with blockchain technologies like Ethereum and Hyperledger Fabric involves following steps –

- **Ethereum**
 - **Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM):** Standardise how smart contracts are deployed on EVM-compatible chains to ensure they perform uniformly.
 - **Data handling:** Standardise data inputs and outputs, especially for complex operations like

calls to other contracts and interactions with decentralized storage.

- **Hyperledger Fabric**

- **Chaincode:** Fabric uses a different approach than EVM. Standardising the development environment and execution model of Chaincode can help in better integration.
- **Private data collections:** Define standards for handling confidential data within contracts, crucial for enterprises.

This paper highlights three critical challenges that need to be addressed in standardisation.

- **Cross-platform communication:** There is a need for reference architectures that support communication between smart contracts on different blockchain platforms. This includes not only the direct interaction between contracts but also the integration of off-chain resources and services.
- **Modularity and scalability:** Current architectures often do not adequately address issues of scalability and modularity. A modular, scalable architecture would allow for parts of the system to be upgraded or replaced without affecting the entire system.
- **Compliance and governance:** Integrating smart contracts into existing ICT ecosystems and ensuring they comply with local regulations and governance models is challenging. A reference architecture should include compliance modules and governance tools that can be adapted to various regulatory environments.

These gaps represent opportunities for development and standardisation in the smart contract domain described in the Section III.

III. PROPOSED STANDARDISATION FRAMEWORK

In response to the identified gaps and challenges, this paper proposes the following standardisation framework and steps.

A. Uniform common requirements for smart contract

This step must establish a core set of uniform and common requirements applicable to various use case domains and blockchain platforms. They should cover –

- **Programmability:** A smart contract must be programmed to accurately generate events, executed via a computer network, and deployed to a blockchain rendering transactions traceable, transparent, and automatically verified.
- **Integrity:** It must be natively supported such that an oracle, a streaming data source that sends event updates, protects against fake events that trigger smart contracts into executing when they should not. Therefore, the smart contract must offer a high degree of protection against functional errors and manipulation by third parties for robustness.
- **Smart contract initiation and termination procedures:** This defines uniform methods for initiating and terminating conditions and procedures

for smart contracts. It must include functionalities like specifying participants to the contracts, setting initial conditions, outlining termination triggers, and fulfillment conditions.

- **Authentication and access control:** Together, they establish the methods following which end users or entities can interact with the smart contract. It should involve defining roles (owner, participant), setting permission levels for interaction (e.g., read, write, execute), and implementing authentication mechanisms.
- **State management with data persistence:** This common requirement refers to how data is stored and updated within the smart contract. It involves defining state variables, specifying allowed data types, and outlining procedures for modifying and reading the data.
- **Dispute resolution protocols:** This establishes a mechanism for handling disagreements arising from smart contract execution. It is therefore a mandatory requirement and covers defining arbitration processes, setting time frames for dispute resolution, and outlining potential recourse options. Smart contracts must have internal functions which can reset the contract or stop its further execution if conditions mentioned in the agreement are not met. For example, if all agreements are not met, payment from the buyer to seller should not be executed.
- **Exception handling and error management:** Another necessary requirement is the specification of protocols for handling unanticipated events or errors during smart contract execution. It should involve defining error codes, outlining corrective actions for different errors, and ensuring the contract remains in a valid state during its entire lifetime of operation.
- The smart contract must integrate protocols for automatically executing the agreements contained within (with or without a digital signature).
- To be legally operational in the European Union, a smart contract and the blockchain network it is deployed to must be GDPR compliant.

B. Unified data formats

Challenges stemming from non-uniform data formats have been highlighted in Section II. Importance of defining common data format for frequently used data types and formats are emphasised in this section for smart contract standardisation. The paper puts forward following steps in this regard.

Standardised data types: A key aspect of the standardisation must cover data types ensuring all smart contracts interpret them identically. The definition should be consistent for formats of fundamental data types like integers (representing quantities), strings (representing text), timestamps (representing time and date), and Boolean (representing true/false values).

Domain specific data formats: While a set of core data types (mentioned above) standardised, industrial use

case domains require additional data types and formats specifically to represent the domain knowledge. For example, the finance use cases may require defining a standardised format for representing currencies and exchange rates between currencies. There must be interoperability at standard formats and methods for data storage, data retrieval, and data communication of a smart contract.

Audit - To maintain auditability, it must be possible to archive transactional data. Therefore, it is mandatory for a smart contract standard to define unified data format and schema for achieving transactional data. That means, the smart contract logic and code must securely store a record of the operations performed on the data in the past of a (terminated) smart contract.

Support for serialisation - Data to be written on the smart contract should support various data serialisation format, e.g., JSON, JSON-LD.

An example of the JSON data format (of a rudimentary smart contract) shown in Fig. 1 records the obligation of the seller and buyer. The agreement from the seller is captured in terms of supplier name, material to be delivered, amount, unit, total cost, currency, and delivery date. The obligation of the buyer is in terms of payment. The link that executes the payment is also provided by the seller. This is a minimum set of data that are recorded in the smart contract for an e-commerce delivery application. The corresponding JSON schema is depicted in Fig. 2.

```
{
  "supplier_name" : "ABC supplier",
  "material_for_delivery" : "furniture",
  "amount" : "1",
  "unit" : "piece",
  "total_cost" : "100",
  "currency" : "EUR",
  "delivery_date" : "15-08-2022",
  "payment" : "https://sentient.digiotouch.app/payment/eur/130"
}
```

Fig. 1. Example of JSON data format reference.

C. Standardised schema

This section proposes a harmonised structure for representing the application logic within the smart contract which acts as a blueprint for building and deploying them in a consistent manner. The proposed standard should encompass five key elements in its schema.

- **Contract definition:** It covers overall purpose and functionalities of the smart contract.
- **Function declarations and parameters:** From a software engineering perspective, it must be including and should outline the functions offered by the contract, along with the data formats expected as input (parameters) for each function.
- **State variables and data types:** This must specify the data the smart contract holds internally (state variables), along with their corresponding data types.
- **Conditional statements and control flow:** This

defines how the contract logic executes based on different conditions occurring. It outlines how the contract makes decisions and progresses through its steps.

```
{
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-04/schema#",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "supplier_name": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "material_for_delivery": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "amount": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "unit": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "total_cost": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "currency": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "delivery_date": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "payment": {
      "type": "string"
    }
  },
  "required": [
    "supplier_name",
    "material_for_delivery",
    "amount",
    "unit",
    "total_cost",
    "currency",
    "delivery_date",
    "payment"
  ]
}
```

- **Event definitions:** This specifies how the contract interacts with the external world. Events might be triggered by specific actions within the contract and can be used to notify external applications or users.
- Fig. 2. JSON schema of the example JSON data format.

Standardising smart contract templates seems outside the scope of ongoing Standard Development Organisations. A library of predefined templates for frequently occurring use cases and common functionalities like creating tokenised assets, managing escrow services, or implementing voting systems will significantly shorten time to development, improve code quality, and enhance re-usability. This paper proposes several steps as a solid foundation to develop smart contract templates.

- **Designing modular and extensible templates:** Smart contract application templates should ideally be modular and extensible that encapsulate business domain specific functionalities and logic. Each template should focus on a single aspect of smart contract functionality, making it easier to reuse, combine, and extend as needed. Modular design facilitates customisation and ensures that contracts remain maintainable and scalable.

- Developing with deployment platform agnostic logic: The templates must be implemented using deployment platform-agnostic programming languages or frameworks. This will assist in ensuring compatibility among different blockchain platforms. For example, using languages like Solidity for Ethereum contracts and Chaincode for Hyperledger Fabric may not be directly portable, but abstracting common logic will help achieve cross-platform compatibility for deployment.

IV. CONCLUSION

In a nutshell, the paper underscores the critical importance of standardisation in smart contract development in blockchain ecosystem to unleash its full potential to industrial applications. Through a systematic gap analysis covering blockchain platforms, current standardisation efforts, the paper has identified key areas where standardisation efforts can significantly enhance the interoperability and efficiency of smart contracts. By addressing the challenges on platform-specific differences, data format inconsistencies, concrete steps are presented for wider adoption and trust in smart contract technology. Collaborative efforts within standards organizations like the IEEE Standards Association, CEN/CENELEC and engagement with industrial stakeholders will be instrumental in achieving such initiatives.

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